

QUALITY SORTING OF SAWN WOOD PRODUCTS USING NIR SPECTROSCOPY AND CHEMOMETRIC MODELS

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing investigation into non-destructive techniques for early wood quality detection holds significant importance in the field of wood construction. This study aimed to develop a rapid and simple approach to detect juvenile (core) or adult (outer) wood in the radial and transversal sections of raw materials used for manufacturing wood products, such as window frames. Two near-infrared (NIR) instruments, one in a laboratory setting and another portable, were employed for this research. The experimental samples included industrially manufactured window profiles containing both juvenile and adult wood. A total of 1500 spectra were collected with both instruments on radial and cross sections in a conditioned environment (65% RH and 20 °C). Preliminary results demonstrate the successful development of robust chemometric models based on NIR spectra and associated analysis. The potential of NIR measurement to detect juvenile and adult wood suggests its use in supporting the quality sorting of sawn wood products.

KEYWORDS: Non-destructive methods, Wood quality detection, Juvenile wood, adult wood

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural wood variability is a great technical challenge for wood processing industries. One of the most important quality features is presence of juvenile wood, which should be minimal in a high-quality product, such as window frames. Core wood, also known as juvenile wood, constitutes the innermost section of the tree trunk near the pith. It represents the primary tissue that experienced rapid growth during the early stages of the tree's life. The characteristics of juvenile wood evolve progressively through successive growth rings until reaching maturity and transforming into adult wood. Juvenile wood has a cellular structure with lower tracheid length, lower density, lower stiffness and cellulose/lignin ratio, higher spiral grain and microfibril angle, and, usually, wider yearly rings [1]. Above mentioned characteristics have deep negative effects on physical-mechanical and technological properties of the material. To ensure proper quality, it is necessary to identify and quantify the presence of juvenile wood. However, the current procedure used for that purpose relies mainly on visual verification. This fact makes necessary the development of an alternative procedure capable of identifying the presence of juvenile wood with higher accuracy and by quick and easy measurements. Various studies have been conducted to determine the point of demarcation between inner-outer wood using different methodologies. These include the use of specific gravity data, where linear regressions, segmented regression or discriminant analysis are widely used to determine the demarcation point [2-3]. In addition, the measurement of the cellulose microfibril angles (MFA) is also used to describe the core-outer wood, as it provides useful information to distinguish regions of the wood, since the MFA are large in the core wood and small in the outer wood [4]. However, these methods require long and careful sample preparation and are not applicable in situ.

1.1 MATERIALS AND METHODS

1.1.1 Materials

Sets of glued wood joints composed of three different boards of Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L) were randomly selected for the NIR measurements. The radial and transversal surfaces of each piece were sanded before measurements and kept conditioned at 20 °C and 65% RH in a dark room before and during the measurements. Zones of juvenile, adult, as well as reaction and heartwood were identified, marked, and measured by both instruments. Spectra were collected on cross and radial sections. In total, 1500 spectra were collected with microNIR and 360 with FT-NIR instrument.

1.1.2 Spectroscopy

Near-infrared spectra were collected using two different instruments, laboratory and portable one. Laboratory Fourier-transform NIR spectrometer:

A Vector N-22 Fourier-transform NIR spectrometer, produced by Bruker Optics GmbH (Ettlingen, Germany), was equipped with a fibre optic probe and operated in the measurement range between 12000 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ (833 to 2500 nm). The spectral wavenumber interval was 3.85 cm⁻¹ with zero-filling equal to 2. The spectral resolution was 8 cm⁻¹ and 32 internal scans were averaged at each spectrum.

Portable Micro-NIR:

A Portable MicroNIR Pro 1700 spectrometer by VIAVI Solutions Inc. (Santa Barbara, USA), integrated with a tungsten lighting lamp and 128-pixel InGaAs photodiode array detector, was used as an alternative instrument. Spectra were acquired with a scanning frequency of 80 Hz, allowing 12.5 ms of the integration time. The effective spectral range covered by the sensor was 950-1650nm (10526 – 6060 cm⁻¹).

1.1.3 Analysis

The data analysis from both instruments was carried out with PLS Toolbox software (Eigenvector Research, Inc.). The pre-treatments applied were normalization (Normalization, SNV), filtering (EMSC, derivatives (Savitzky-Golay 1st and 2nd derivative)), scaling (Mean Centre), and removal of some wavelength regions. Then different analyses were performed in order to obtain the most suitable model for our goal (Figure 1). The classification was done by PLS-DA, SVM, KNN, and SIMCA methods.

Figure 1. Raw signals and preprocessing

2 RESULTS

2.1 CLASSIFICATION

Support Vector Machine (SVM) as a pre-processing step was identified as the optimal approach, providing the highest discrimination between juvenile and adult wood. The classification success for juvenile and adult wood using FT-NIR and Micro-NIR with these chemometric models was 83% and 92.7%, respectively. The independent validation set, comprised of diverse wood samples used for calibration, demonstrated high accuracy in discriminating juvenile wood (100%) and adult wood (81.3%). Extension of the models with spectra from reaction and heartwood resulted in a 100% success rate for discriminating reaction wood and 45.5% for heartwood (Tables 1,2). These preliminary findings highlight the high feasibility of NIR spectroscopy in discriminating juvenile and adult wood., the preliminary results prove a high feasibility for NIR spectroscopy in the discrimination of juvenile and adult wood.

Table 1. Prediction of model of FT-NIR

FT-NIR	Adult	Heart	Juvenile	Reaction
Predicted as adult	77	8	21	31
Predicted as heart	8	77	0	23
Predicted as juvenile	15	15	64	0
Predicted as reaction	0	0	14	46
Unassigned	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Prediction of model of Micro-NIR

Micro-NIR	Adult	Heart	Juvenile	Reaction
Predicted as adult	81	55	0	0
Predicted as heart	0	45	0	0
Predicted as juvenile	11	0	100	0
Predicted as reaction	7	0	0	100

Unassigned	0	0	0	0
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Figure 2 illustrates the Hotellings T2 versus Q residuals, which helps to explain how precise the model was in describing a given class (core-transition-outer). The samples belonging to the assigned classes fit within the 95% Qlimit, which was a good indicator of the model performance. The initial findings indicate the successful development of robust models based on NIR spectra for the detection of juvenile wood. Consequently, these models have the potential to support the quality sorting of sawn wood products. However, the model developed has to be extensively validated to deal with other sources of wood variability as related to the provenance, defect presence, or drying history.

Figure 2. Class discriminations results (Hotellings T2 versus Q residuals)

3 CONCLUSIONS

The preliminary results show that it was possible to develop robust models based on NIR spectra for the discrimination between juvenile, adult, and heartwood. Therefore, these models have the potential to support the quality sorting of sawn wood products. However, the model developed has to be extensively validated to deal with other sources of wood variability.

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